

Time Requirements
of
Hard- versus Soft-Copy Interpretation
of
SICU Computed Radiographic Images

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Abstract

The Brooke Army Medical Center PACS was used to produce paired hard copy and soft copy interpretations of computed radiography images of SICU patients for eight days. There was no statistical difference in the time spent setting up and reading hard copy vs. the setup and reading time for soft copy interpretation. The time required for the radiologists to display and read the soft copy studies was 33% longer than the time required to view and interpret the same hard copy studies which had been previously placed on a film rotator.

Introduction

Brooke Army Medical Center has a picture archiving and communication system (PACS) and is in transition to filmless radiology. To accomplish this transition, a change in interpretation activity from film to monitor-based reading sessions was required. The first step in this transition was the conversion of the hospital's Burn Unit SICU from a hard copy radiologic interpretation to a soft copy radiologic interpretation. In this transition period our PACS produced a hard copy of each radiograph as well as images which were viewed using high resolution monitors. Because the Burn Unit film rotator was still being used by the SICU surgeons, there was an excellent opportunity to compare the time requirements of interpreting these images from hard versus soft copy format.

Materials and Methods

For soft copy images the Brooke Army Medical Center PACS, called the Medical

Diagnostic Imaging Support (MDIS) System [1] (Loral Western Development Laboratories, San Jose, CA), was used to acquire, verify and interpret the images. The system consists of a central computer, with an array of hard drives for storage of active images and an optical disk juke box for archival purposes. Soft copy images were interpreted on the Soft Copy Image Display (SCID-4A), which consists of a Macintosh II-FX (Apple Computers, Inc., Cupertino, CA) computer platform with custom video display cards manufactured by Loral, which output to four gray scale 2K monitors (22 inch diagonal, 1536x2048 pixel, Tektronix Inc., Beaverton, OR). The Macintosh II-FX is connected to the central computer via 100 megabit/sec optical fibers for image data transfer and 10 megabit/sec twisted pair ethernet for character data. The software running on the system was Vantage release 3.01 (Loral Medical Imaging Systems, Hoffman Estates, IL).

The process to acquire Computed Radiography (CR) images is as follows: A cassette containing the photo-stimulatable phosphor plate is placed behind the patient. The patient is then exposed to a conventional X-ray beam, which passes through the patient and exposes the plate. The cassette is then placed in a CR reader, which removes the plate from the cassette and scans the plate with a laser to produce a digital sequence which can be viewed as an image. The image is first reviewed by the radiologic technologist or a quality control technologist in a process called verifying. In this quality control step, the images are rotated and/or inverted as needed to obtain proper orientation. Gray scale can also be adjusted for optimal viewing.

Once the study has been verified, it will appear on unread work lists for interpretation by a radiologist with the orientation and gray scale selected during the verification process as the default presentation to the radiologist.

At the workstation, the radiologist must select the format for viewing examinations. In this study, all examinations were viewed with one-image-per-monitor (one-on-one) format. Examinations were interpreted in comparison to prior examinations of the same type (Portable Chest, for example). This is accomplished using a software option called Default Display Protocol (DDP). When DDP is enabled the computer will place the examination to be read on the right-most monitor and place the current patient's last three consecutive images of the same type on the monitors to the left in descending chronological order. Thus, the study can be read in comparison to prior studies just as on a conventional film rotator. The gray scale and contrast can be adjusted and the images can be magnified to improve interpretation.

When the radiologist is finished dictating the study, a single key-stroke command closes the current examination and the next unread examination and comparison images are displayed. The examination just interpreted is removed from the unread list, its status is changed from "unread" to "dictated", and it then appears on the transcriptionist's work list signifying the completion of the dictation process.

Hard copy images were printed by the CR scanner on 25.7 x 36.4 cm Fuji Medical CR Film (Fuji Photo Film Co., LTD, Fujinomyia, Japan). For hard copy interpretation, the films were displayed on a Panoramascope Mass Film Viewer, Model 400MD (Radx Corporation, Houston, TX).

To compare the time requirements of interpreting the Brooke Army Medical Center Burn Unit radiographic images hard copy versus soft copy, the following protocol was used:

The burn unit images were read for eight days. For four of the days the images

were read and dictated hard copy first and then soft copy. On the other days, the studies were first read and dictated soft copy and then hard copy. To avoid duplicate transcriptions, only the dictation's from the soft copy images were transcribed. As close as possible, the same dictations were performed at either read-out session unless new observations were made. A fourth-year radiology resident with over two years experience on the MDIS system was used to perform all readings.

The hard copy interpretation sessions were conducted as follows:

Each day the Burn Unit films were sorted into the same order as they were hung on the rotator. The current studies were then placed on the rotator next to any old examinations. If room was not available, an old film was taken down. The time to sort and hang the hard copy films was recorded as was the number of films hung. Once all the films were hung, each new film was then interpreted and the amount of time to interpret and dictate each film was recorded.

The soft copy interpretation sessions were conducted as follows:

The radiologist logged on to the workstation. The "examinations-by-referring-service" queue was checked to see if all Burn Unit exams were verified. Any unverified examinations were marked as verified. The burn unit unread work list was opened, and one-on-one format and Default Display Protocol were selected as defaults. This preparation time was recorded. The radiologist read each examination soft copy and the time to read each study was recorded. Change of gray scale, or use of magnification was noted.

All results were tabulated and statistical analysis was performed with The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software (SPSS/PC+ V2.0, SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL).

Results

Of 194 hard and soft copy images theoretically available for this study, only 180 images were actually available,

consisting of 83 pairs of duplicate hard & soft copy images. There were 14 soft copy images without corresponding hard copy images. This represents a 14.4% missing film rate (14/97) at the time of interpretation. These missing studies consisted of two cervical spines, six chests, and six shoulders images. There was no incidence in which there was a hard copy image without corresponding soft copy image presented for interpretation. There were seven images not marked as Burn Unit examinations, but these were present in the patient's master digital folder. The time to read these examinations was included in the study, but the time to call up the master jacket was not included. It was felt that recording the time required to find lost examinations would give soft copy too great an advantage and is not included in this report. Thus comparison interpretation time measurements involved only examinations where both soft and hard copy images were available (n=83 image pairs in 71 examinations). There was a significant ($p < 0.000$) difference between the preparation time for hard (33 seconds/image) compared to the soft copy (9 seconds/image) format. The hard copy preparation time consisted of the time to manually sort films and place them on the film rotator divided by the number of new images. The soft copy preparation time consisted of the sum of the time for the radiologist to log on to the workstation, check the unread work lists for unverified exams and mark them verified, and set appropriate defaults. This sum was then divided by the number of new images, to match the units of the hard copy preparation time. There was also a significant difference ($p < 0.000$) in the time required to display and interpret the exams hard copy (84 seconds/image) compared to soft copy (112 seconds/image). This difference is equal to 28 seconds/image, making soft copy interpretation 33% slower than hard copy display and interpretation of films previously placed on a film rotator. The soft copy interpretation time included the time to display and read the images. The hard copy interpretation time included the

time for the rotator to move to the next panel with unread films and for that exam to be read.

If the above preparation and display/interpretation times are summed, there was no significant difference ($p = 0.441$) found between the total time required to manually sort, hang and interpret hard copy films (117 sec./exam) compared to the time to log on, mark unverified exams as verified, set appropriate defaults and then view and interpret the same images in soft copy format (121 sec./image). A paired samples t-test showed no significant difference in reading times within hard or soft copy readings when the examinations were read first as hard or soft copy. Interpretation times per image were significantly different with respect to examination type (chest, KUB, shoulder, etc.) because of one bilateral wrist /hand examination. This study had six images and required a long dictation because every digit on both hands was destroyed to varying degrees by the patient's burn injury. When this examination was excluded from the data analysis, no statistically significant difference in hard versus soft copy reading time was attributable to examination type (ANOVA, $p = 0.626$).

No significant difference was noted between Orthopedic (extremity) and non extremity reading times. Differences in reading times per image between exams with different number of images was significant (ANOVA, $p = 0.0001$), with or without inclusion of the bilateral wrist/hand exam. As shown in Table 1 below, the examinations with multiple images are generally interpreted with less time per image than studies with fewer images per exam. This trend was more prominent in hard copy than soft copy interpretation. Within exams read hard copy, differences in reading time per image between exams with different number of images were significant (ANOVA, $p = 0.0000$). Also within the exams read soft copy, differences in reading time per image between exams with different number of images were significant (ANOVA, $p = 0.001$).

Table 1
Hard and Soft Copy Interpretation Times
by
Number of Images per Exam

Images per Exam	N (exams)	Reading Time (Seconds/image)			
		Hard Copy		Soft Copy	
		Mean	StDev	Mean	StDev
1	64	88.8	23.4	118.8	37.2
2	5	38.4	11.4	44.4	15.0
3	1	19.8		45.6	
6	1	37.2		43.8	

Significance:

ANOVA between hard copy groups: $p = 0.0000$

ANOVA between soft copy groups: $p = 0.001$

ANOVA between hard and soft copy, by number of images per exam: $p=0.24$

There was no significant difference between hard and soft copy interpretation times by number of images per exam (a two factor ANOVA with repeated measures on one factor analysis,

$p=0.24$). This non-significance is likely due to the small sample size in some of the number-of-images-per-exam groups. The distribution of exam types by number of images per exam is shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Distribution of Exams Types
by
Images per Exam

Images per Exam	Chest	KUB	Shoulder	Forearm	Elbow	Leg	Wrist
1	51	12	1				
2	1			2	2		
3						1	
6							1

The soft copy data was analyzed for differences in reading time with use of software tools and whether or not the exam was verified by the radiologist. The radiologist verifying an examination required an extra 18 seconds or 18% longer than exams requiring no extra software manipulation or no verification by the radiologist, but this was not significant. Window/level adjustments required 35 seconds or a 35% increase in time over exams not requiring software tool manipulation or radiologist verification. Magic glass, which allows one to simultaneously change

window/leveling and magnification within a portion of the image, required 68 seconds or 67% longer than exams not requiring software tool manipulation or verification by the radiologist. The major effort in this study was to examine differences in time requirements of hard versus soft copy readouts of computed radiography images; however, the following resolution-related data was also obtained: The distal portions of nasogastric/feeding tubes were seen on soft copy in all 39 chest images with such tubes in place, compared to 28 out of 37 times (76%) with hard copy images.

Two hard copy chest radiographs with nasogastric tubes on the corresponding soft copy were lost. In each of the nine instances of non-visualization of the distal nasogastric tube, the tube end was lost in the mediastinal or upper abdominal shadow on the hard copy CR film. In all nine instances, the nasogastric tube could be visualized all the way to the bottom of the soft copy image, but only with the aid of "Magic Glass". All endotracheal tubes, chest tubes and vascular catheters were seen throughout their course with either hard or soft copy format. One pneumothorax was found. This examination was read hard copy first (which required 136 seconds) and the pneumothorax was not detected. It was detected on the soft copy reading (which required 149 seconds) without any image enhancement or use of software tools. In retrospect, it was felt that the pneumothorax was equally obvious on soft and hard copy and was found on soft copy because that format was utilized

second on that day; therefore, the radiologist had greater cumulative time looking at the image when viewed during the second reading session.

Discussion

Few radiologists hang their own ICU films; therefore, the 33% more time to dictate images soft copy as compared to dictating pre-hung hard copy films is the more important number. This would also mean that hard copy is 24% faster than soft copy reading and corresponds well to Leckie's finding that hard copy reading of pre-hung ICU films is 27% faster than reading soft copy [2].

The MDIS system has a "dictation macro" which performs these tasks with a single key stroke. If the radiologist were reading an examination in the unread work list and pressed the dictation macro, the following events occur with respect to time:

Table 3
Sequence of Events by Time
Which Occur While Dictating
a Soft Copy SICU Chest Examination

Time (Sec)	Activity	Comments
0	Press the dictation macro	The computer searches for the next unread examination and comparison examinations and begins to transfer them down optical fibers to the workstation for display. You wait.
7	Clear all four monitors	Wait.
18	Show next patient's name and examination type, date, time, etc.	Only now can you start dictating by giving the examination identification data.
18	Display first examination	Start interpreting...
29	Display second examination	...and comparing...
34	Display third examination	
39	Display fourth examination	
101	Dictation complete	Assuming no software tools used
112	Dictation complete	Average for this study
118	Dictation complete	If an image needed verified.
135	Dictation complete	If an image needed a window/level change
168	Dictation complete	If "Magic Glass" tool was used.

Note in table 3 that one must wait 18 seconds before the beginning dictation, because the patient and examination demographics are not yet available. This is very important because the difference in reading pre-hung hard copy to soft copy is only 28 seconds more per image. If this data could be displayed earlier, the difference would be down to about 10 seconds, or only 12% longer.

What would be even better is a Picture Archiving, Communication and Dictation System. If the dictation system were part of the same computer system showing the images to the radiologist, the computer could embed the exam demographics and the radiologists name in the header of each dictation, saving an 15 seconds (17.8%) on each dictation. With such a system, a clinician could view any study on the system, and if the exam was dictated but not yet transcribed, he or she could click on a "listen" icon to hear the dictation or the final impression. The digital recording of the dictation would be removed after the exam was transcribed to preserve database space.

On a representative examination, 39 seconds were required for the system to locate the examinations and transfer them to the workstation for display after the dictation macro was started. From seconds 39 to 112, a period of 73 seconds, the radiologist is dictating. If the dictation macro on the local workstation were to be interrogating the central computer to start the transfer of the next examination and comparison examinations during the 73 seconds the radiologist was dictating, then, when the radiologist presses the dictation macro key again, the data could already be in memory on the workstation display boards. This change would give the illusion that the data had been transferred nearly instantaneously, without change in the speed of the fiber optics. Only a change in software and increased display memory would be required.

One of the great advantages of digital imaging is the ability to use image-enhancing software tools. Changing the window/level took an average of 34 more seconds or 34% longer.

If this were a plain film we would have used the hot light if the area in question were dark or might have required a retake film at a different exposure. A repeat examination would be even more likely if the region of concern was under-exposed.

Although a 34% increase in interpretation time is substantial, it is much shorter than repeating the examination and has no increased patient radiation dose. It should also be noted that we did not hot light the hard copy films in this study because these were CR films. The image processing algorithm used by the CR reader to print the images, prints all pixels which are above a certain value (high on the shoulder of the processing curve) to black; therefore, hot lighting a CR film in these dark area, doesn't usually provide more information. Since we did not hot light the hard copy films, they were read faster.

The use of the "Magic Glass" software tool took 67% more time than viewing the an image without software tools. This tool is a combination magnifying glass and gray-scale adjuster. It allowed us to follow nasogastric/feeding tubes till their termination or to the edge of the image 100% of the time on soft copy as compared to 75% of the time with the hard copy CR images. Since both hard and soft copy images are from the same digital data this may suggest the printing algorithm used by the CR printer may be giving us an effective under visualization of the mediastinum. Because of gray scale display limitations, no single hard copy film will ever be able to show all the data which can be displayed from a monitor where gray scale and magnification can be manipulated. No matter how sophisticated the software, it will probably always take longer to examine that extra data, but studies so examined should be better read.

The data of this study show that as the number of images per exam goes up, the interpretation time per image goes down, but that this time savings is greater with hard copy than soft copy reading format. Because this was a study of SICU

images, most were portable chest exams with one image per film, and there was an insufficient number of multiple image exams to make this trend statistically significant.

The hard copy film loss rate of 14% is excessive but similar to the 16% rate reported by Gold [3] at a trauma center prior to implementing a PACS in radiology. Eight out of the 14 missing examinations (57%) were orthopedic examinations even though orthopedic radiographs accounted for only 11% of the study. Our orthopedic department is in a different hospital building and they are frequently consulted for injuries to burn patients. The hard copy films are frequently taken back to the rotator in their conference room. Many of these "missing" films were no doubt on that rotator.

Lastly, as much as we would like to point out that the single pneumothorax was missed on the hard copy but seen on soft copy, it is probably wisest not to draw any conclusions from a sample size of one.

Conclusion

The Brooke Army Medical Center MDIS PACS can deliver improved interrogation of SICU computed radiographs without a difference in time spent sorting, hanging, reading and dictating images; however, there is a 33% increase in radiologist interpretation/dictation time as compared to hard copy CR films previously placed on a film rotator. Future hardware and software advances will decrease this time differential.

References

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